

DISTRIBUTION OF TRACE ELEMENTS IN BIOLOGICAL MATERIAL.

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In continuation of previous work, representative types of cereals, pulses and leafy vegetables have been analysed and the results reported in this paper. Methods devised for the spectrographic analysis of mineral substances have been applied for the identification and estimation of trace elements. Many interesting results have been obtained in this way. It is pointed out that the methods should be specially useful to those interested in problems of animal and human nutrition.

The wide distribution of elements in minute quantities in biological materials has been regarded until lately as accidental. In recent years, a number of papers have been published on the presence of trace elements such as Mn, Ti, B, Zn in soil and the marked influence they exert on the microbial population and on plant growth. The importance of traces of manganese for the plant has been demonstrated by McHargue, McLean, Kelley and Gerrestsen (*Trans. Third Int. Cong. Soil Sci.*, 1935, 1, 189). The occurrence of molybdenum and vanadium in nature has been well studied by Meulen (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1932, 51, 549), Dingwell (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1934, 11, 32), Horner (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1934, 48, 981) and others. Hoagland (*Trans. Int. Cong. Soil Sci.*, 1935, 3, 216) found that zinc salts have a striking curative effect in diseases of fruit trees, known as "mottled leaf". Author's own experiments (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937 6B, 91) have shown that soil fertility is in a measure due to the predominating proportion of manganese and zinc.

Hart and co-workers have shown (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 77, 797) the importance of copper as a supplement to iron for haemoglobin regeneration in the rat. Manganese was found by Wilgaus, Norris and Heuser (*J. Nutrition*, 1937, 14, 155) and Caskey and others (*ibid.*, 1939, 17, 407) to be markedly effective in preventing the incidence of "perosis" in chicks. The rôle of zinc in the nutrition of rats and pre-school age children has been investigated by Stirn and others (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1935, 109, 347) and Scouler (*J. Nutrition*, 1939, 17, 103). The deleterious effects of molybdenum on milking cattle has been pointed out by Lewis and co-workers (*Nature*, 1938, 141, 553).

Very little work has been done in India on the rôle of these micro-constituents in animal and human nutrition and no attempts have been made to estimate quantitatively the amounts of such elements as Mn, Zn, Mo in some of the widely consumed Indian foodstuffs. The only references

in the literature in this direction are those of Boyd and Dey (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1933, **21**, 109), Rudra (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 132) and Newcomb and Sankaran (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1929, **16**, 788) regarding the quantitative estimation of manganese. Before any work could be undertaken on the nutritive value of a particular foodstuff, complete data regarding the distribution of major and the minor constituents of the foods will be invaluable.

For the detection and estimation of the minor constituents micro-chemical methods have been and are being widely used. The superiority of spectrographic methods has been previously pointed out by the author (*loc. cit.*).

In continuation of the previous work (*Science & Culture*, 1938, **4**, 362) further representative types of cereals, pulses and leafy vegetables have been analysed and the results are reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In preparing the samples for analysis they were carefully washed with distilled water, spread out in thin layers and left until the water had evaporated. They were then cut into small pieces, dried to a constant weight at 100°, ground in a glass mortar and bottled. The samples were ignited over a Bunsen flame in a platinum crucible at a temperature less than 450°. This method of ashing gave entirely satisfactory results and the use of a muffle seemed quite unnecessary. Provided that the flame is not allowed to play directly on the specimen, there is no reason to suppose the possibility of contamination with the material of the burner.

For photographing the spectra, a Hilger medium quartz spectrograph was used. The plates used for the ultraviolet and near ultraviolet were "Imperial Special Rapid," while for the visible region "Eastman Panchromatic" plates, which have a considerable and fairly uniform sensitivity from 6,700 to 4,000 Å were used.

The arc spectra of the elements contained in the above specimens were excited using silver and graphite electrodes. Owing to the low temperature of the silver arc some elements like Mn, Ni, Co, and B might escape detection. Further it was felt that for other elements good corroboration could be obtained by comparing results in both types of arc. The electrodes were supplied by Adam Hilger and reported to be H. S. brand purity and accompanied by full chemical and spectroscopic reports on their composition. The electrodes were prepared so that the positive rod contained a cavity 2 mm. wide and 4 mm. deep into which weighed amounts of the sample were introduced. The negative was sharpened to a fine

point. This pointed electrode aided in centering and confining the arc, thereby reducing its tendency to wander. The variation of the arc current was never more than ± 0.05 ampere.

The essential feature of the method used in the course of this work for the determination of the concentration is a comparison of the line intensities. Spectrograms were obtained from prepared samples made up in concentrations from 1 part in 100 down to the limit of sensitivity. The particular line chosen for the determination of the element was microphotographed in all the spectra and a curve was constructed showing the relation between the percentage of the element and the intensity produced on the photographic plate. From the known intensity of the line in the test spectrum, the percentage composition of the element could be determined by interpolation from the curve.

While this paper contents itself with a qualitative identification of the major elements, a quantitative estimation is done for Mn, Zn, and Mo. For the detection and estimation of Zn, the line 2138.6\AA , the most sensitive of zinc lines was used, while for Mo the three lines 3798, 3864, and 3903\AA which form the "raies ultimes" were used. For Mn, the triplet $4034.45, 4033.07, 4030.76\text{\AA}$ was adopted.

Four different samples of each were analysed and the average results of estimations are given in Table I. Typical spectrograms are shown in Plates I and II.

TABLE I.

English name.	Bot. name.	Moisture.	Ash.	Mn	Zn	Mo	Remarks.
				expressed per kg. of dry materials.			
Rice (polished)	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	12.4%	1.19%	12.6 mg	2.0 mg	0.1 to 0.72 mg.	There was a wide variation from sample to sample, so only the limits are given and it can be said that cereals vary within these limits as regards their Mo content
Wheat (whole grain)	<i>Triticum vulgare</i>	12.8	1.30	36.4	20.4		
Bengal gram	<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	5.8	3.03	28.6	19.4	2.0	
Black gram	<i>Phaseolus mungo</i>	10.9	3.70	24.0	26.5	4.5	
Peas (green)	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	78.6	4.10	18.1	40.2	9.4	
Amaranth (tender)	<i>Amaranthus gangeticus</i>	86.1	23.1	60.2	26.8	< 1	
Spinach	<i>Spinacea oleracea</i>	92.3	23.3	82.3	62.3	} Purchase present only in very minute traces.	
Cabbage	<i>Brassica oleracea capitata</i>	92.4	11.2	11.3	23.5		

DISCUSSION.

From the spectrograms reproduced the variation in the concentration of the different elements is very striking. There is a continuous increase in the proportion of sodium and alkaline earth metals and iron as we go from cereals to pulses and leafy vegetables.

The leafy vegetables are generally rich in iron though spinach contains comparatively less of this element. It is seen from the results that wheat is comparatively rich in manganese than rice and it is interesting to draw attention to the work of McCarrison (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1927, **14**, 64r) on the effect of Mn in foodstuffs and its bearing on the growth of animals. We have an analogy of the favourable effects of manganese on plant growth and the results reported here also support the observations of McCarrison, and suggest that it plays a definite rôle in human nutrition as well. Molybdenum is found in fairly large amounts in all pulses, peas and black gram containing the largest amounts. Next in order are the cereals, and the leafy vegetables contain the least amounts of Mo which is present only in very minute traces. Nickel is present in small but detectable quantities. The evidence for Co and vanadium is not definite. The observations of Boyd and De (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1933, **20**, 78g) regarding the presence of vanadium in rice and wheat could not be verified. The cereals are relatively rich in Rb and Sr. The most remarkable feature is the extraordinarily high magnesium content of spinach.

It would seem from the results that the so called trace elements are really present in appreciable amounts and would possibly play a definite and specific rôle in animal and human nutrition. The assessment of the nutritive value of a particular foodstuff would be incomplete without a proper understanding of the exact rôle of these minor constituents.

Explanation of Plates.

The spectrograms reproduced here are enlargements of certain regions of the spectra of representative specimens of cereals, pulses and leafy vegetables with the blank spectra of electrodes.

Plate I: Fig. 1. shows the Sr line 4608 intensified in wheat.

In each of the other figures, (a) is the spectrum of the blank electrodes; b, c, d are the spectra of rice, black gram and spinach respectively; e is the spectrum of Ag arc comparison.

Plate II, Figure 4 shows comparison standards for estimating zinc:

PLATE I

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

FIG. 4(A)

